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CARTPT expression is activated in the brains of humans with epilepsy.

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Seizure disorders can be severe and intractable, requiring invasive procedures that aim to grossly limit electrical activity by surgical methods. We used whole transcriptome technologies to discover molecules whose function is likely to contribute to pathology in the seizure disorder epilepsy. We describe here perturbed expression of the neuropeptide *CARTPT* in the brains of humans with epilepsy.